

IPBES VA Chapter 3. Valuation Atlas. Systematic Review on Valuation methods and Valuation uptake.

Code: IPBES_VA_3.7

Versioning: 01 (05.03.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6468906

Project leader(s)

Mette Termansen (mt@ifro.ku.dk)

David Barton (David.Barton@nina.no)

Aidin Niamir (niamir@gmail.com)

Researcher(s)

Sander Jacobs (sander.jacobs@inbo.be)

Cem Iskender Aydın (cemiaydin@gmail.com)

Yann Laurans (yann.laurans@sciencespo.fr)

Joy Kumagai (joy.kumagai@senckenberg.de)

Data curator(s)

David González-Jiménez (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Victoria Contreras (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapters 3 and 4. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of Chapter 3 that will assess different valuation methodologies and approaches, including (a) biophysical, social and cultural, economic, health and holistic (including indigenous and local community-based) and (b) approaches for the integration of different types of values. And the mandate of Chapter 4 that states that *Chapter 4* should address values and valuation in relation to decision-making and policymaking at different levels and in different contexts, placing special importance on those methods that have been uptaken by decision-making. To provide the necessary evidence for Chapters 3¹ and 4² this Systematic review was performed.

¹ Systematic PCIV (Principles, Criteria, Indicators, Verifiers) review on valuation methods (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4404678>).

²Systematic review on valuation uptake (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4391335>)

Process overview

miro

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: 'Valuation Atlas. Systematic Review on Valuation methods and Valuation uptake'.

Search languages: English

Search engine: Web of Science

Exact search date: 6 May 2020

Sample extracted: 79 040 papers

Search terms: See **(R1)** for the extended search terms (VA_3.7 PCIV search terms (R1)). The period of publication used for the search was set from January 1981 - March 2020.

In general, the logic behind keyword selection was that papers should be:

- i) about nature or biodiversity,
- ii) should be an application of valuation methods/approaches,
- iii) should focus on at least one of the value dimensions that we work with in the assessment,
- iv) has the purpose to support decision-making (understood in a broad sense).

To be selected for review a paper had to include a combination of search terms in the NATURE & BIODIVERSITY lists, the VALUE list, DECISION-MAKING PURPOSE list, and the METHODS list in the titles, key words or abstracts of the paper.

Fields extracted:

- Authors (AU)
- Title (TI)
- Journal (SO)
- ISO Source abbreviation (JI)
- Abstract (AB)
- Author keywords (DE)
- Keywords Plus® (ID)
- Language (LA)
- Document Type (DT)
- Web of Science core collection times cited count (TC)
- Author address (C1)
- Digital Object Identifier (DI)
- Publisher Address (PA)
- Article number (AR)
- Editors (BE)
- Funding (FU)
- Publisher (PU)
- Funding text (FX)
- International standard book number (ISBN) (BN)
- International standard serial number (ISSN) (SN)
- Part number (PN)
- Pages (PP)
- Volume (VL)
- Year Published (PY)
- Accession number (UT)
- Cited reference count (NR)
- Research areas (SC)
- Usage count (since 2013) (U2)
- Web of Science categories (WC)
- E-mail Address (EM)
- Book series title (SE)
- Document delivery number (GA)
- Book title (BO)
- Reprint address (RP)
- Database (DB)
- Cited references (CR)

Location and format of the data (A): IPBES_VA 3.7

Corpus_06May20_GEONames_TS_16June20 (A).csv

Treatment applied: (R2) Geographical names extraction. The country names were extracted from fields TI, AB, DE, ID, CI, FU, FX in document (A). They were grouped as (TI, AB, DE, ID) and (CI,FU,FX). Then, they were added to the same document with their ISO 3 codes (<https://www.iso.org/iso-3166-country-codes.html>) as fields:

CountryName_TI_AB_DE_ID

CountryName_CI_FU_FX CI & FU & FX

Treatment applied (R2): IPBES regions and subregions. The country names were later merged by IPBES regions and subregions. IPBES regions and subregions obtained from <https://zenodo.org/record/3928281> These were added to document (A) in fields:

Region_TI_AB_DE_ID

Region_CI_FU_FX

Subregion_TI_AB_DE_ID

Subregion_CI_FU_FX

Sample extracted: 48 781 papers

Analysis of the data: A descriptive analysis of the meta data retrieved from the papers was performed and can be found here:

https://jkumagai96.github.io/VA_version2/Valuation_atlas.html. The main topics that were reviewed in this analysis are: the geographic distribution of the papers and the organizations conducting the research, along with the number of publications per organization and, their temporal trends; and an analysis of indicators using the IPBES Core Indicators (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4439411>).

Analysis of the data: In parallel this Systematic review was used by Chapters 3 and 4 to provide the evidence that support both chapters (See *Chapter 3 Systematic PCIV review on valuation methods and Chapter 4 Systematic review on valuation uptake*).

Documents attached:

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA 3.7 Corpus_06May20_GEONames_TS _16June20 (A)	.csv	326.3 MB	CORPUS database with 79 040 papers obtained in the Systematic search in Web of Science.
R1	VA_3.7 PCIV search terms (R1)	.pdf	122 KB	Search terms used to obtain the CORPUS
R1	VA_3.7 PCIV search terms (R1)	.wos	139 KB	Search terms used to obtain the CORPUS in wos format